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Preliminary Report

Complete Remission of Obsessive Thoughts in H63D Syndrome Type-3 (Oshtoran Syndrome) Patients Following Corticosteroid Therapy

Abstract

This preliminary report outlines clinical observations of two patients diagnosed with H63D Syndrome Type-3, also known as Oshtoran Syndrome. A 42-year-old woman from Malaysia and a 38-year-old man from Iran presented with complete remission of their obsessive thoughts caused by Oshtoran Syndrome. Alongside the administration of the Amitradicain formula, both patients received a high-dose corticosteroid treatment, resulting in the disappearance of all neuropsychiatric symptoms.

Setting

This preliminary report holds significant importance beyond the scope of H63D Syndrome. It is published with the conviction that the observed phenomena are not exclusive to Oshtoran Syndrome but likely extend to PANS Syndrome, which shares

immunological pathogenesis markers with H63D Syndrome Type-3.

Patient 1

A 42-year-old Malaysian woman met all criteria for Oshtoran Syndrome (H63D Syndrome Type-3) and was admitted to a psychiatric facility due to unbearable obsessive thoughts. After a thorough examination by the departments of Internal Medicine (including Endocrinology and Hematology) and Psychiatry, and excluding other diseases, Oshtoran Syndrome was diagnosed. She was treated with the Amitradicain formula and 30mg of Prednisolone daily in the morning. A marked improvement in obsessive thoughts was observed within a day of starting corticosteroid therapy. By day 12, she was free from any neuropsychiatric symptoms for the first time in 31 years. The treatment continued for another eight weeks before tapering down Prednisolone, which resulted in the return of neuropsychiatric symptoms. Notably, there was evidence of Substantia nigra degeneration linked to the basal ganglia on TCS.

Patient 2

A 38-year-old man was hospitalized in the City of Tehran following a failed suicide attempt. After seven weeks of treatment according to standard guidelines and worsening symptoms under SSRIs, a psychiatric colleague suspected Oshtoran Syndrome, particularly due to SSRI intolerance and the typical liver affection in H63D Syndrome Type-3. Following transfer to the Medical Clinic for Gastroenterology, Metabolism, and Hepatology, and three weeks of intensive diagnostics, Oshtoran Syndrome (H63D Syndrome Type-3) was diagnosed. Treatment began with high-dose Amitradicain

infusion every 4 hours and 55mg Prednisolone in the morning. Improvements were noted hours after treatment commencement, with obsessive thoughts disappearing within 72 hours. The patient was neuropsychiatrically stable upon discharge. The Corticosteroid was carefully tapered to 5mg from week 12, maintaining approximately 15% improvement, although a resurgence of obsessive thought disorders was not surprising given the structural damage to the Substantia nigra (TCS finding).

Discussion

The notion that obsessive thoughts can have an organic origin has been established since the identification of PANS/PANDAS Syndrome, which shares a presumed pathomechanism with Oshoran Syndrome. The efficacy of corticosteroids in ameliorating inflammation-induced obsessive thoughts is known but underreported. The consideration of H63D Syndrome in Patient 2, given the deterioration under SSRIs, is notable and characteristic of all three forms of H63D Syndrome.

Conclusion

Further research is urgently needed to determine whether anti-inflammatory pharmacotherapy can aid patients with organic obsessive-compulsive disorders of other etiologies. The intersection of Neurology/Endocrinology and Psychiatry presents a promising avenue for exploration and treatment innovation.

Conflict of interests

None

References

The references will follow in the final report.